

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19860759

ONLINE REPURCHASE INTENTION: A FOCUS ON UTILITARIAN FACTORS

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Received: 15/03/2026
Accepted: 17/04/2026

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ABSTRACT

Online Repurchase Intention is deemed to be the consequence of miscellaneous factors, such as E-trust, Perceived risks, Perceived usefulness, Perceived ease and Website reputation. Each of these factors play different roles in shaping the customer's Online Repurchase behavior. When a customer feels safe through Website reputation and ease of use, he/she intends to repeat the purchase decision and enhance his/her digital experience. To highlight these roles, an explanatory model of the intention to repurchase online, integrating social/psychological antecedents, utility antecedents (Perceived usefulness and Perceived ease of use), and an antecedent relating to Website reputation was implemented. The empirical study, carried out with 220 customers using the linear regression method, was conducted to show how long these factors could be intended to key success factors that push customer to repurchase products from the same website.

KEYWORDS: Online Repurchase Intention, Perceived ease of use, Perceived usefulness, E-trust, Perceived risk, Website reputation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Through several available channels, dedicated for carrying out transactions and interacting with companies, consumer behavior has changed thoroughly. Today, instead of going to Bricks-and-Mortar businesses, customers can buy products and services online. Online shopping offers customers greater convenience, flexibility, timesaving, reduced costs, product information and competitive prices. Moreover, customers become able to get rid of time or place constraints to accomplish their transactions. Access to products or services is achieved with just few clicks (Adnan, 2014). E-commerce also has an impact on the sales performance of vendors, since they can use this new channel to target customers who prefer to buy online (Guan & Cheng, 2009) rather than in stores or physical outlets.

However, the interaction between seller and customer during online purchases rises few concerns. Privacy and the problem of confidentiality of personal data and the uncertainties linked to the products on the processing of orders are arising for some customers, with the result that online purchases are still perceived as riskier than Mortar-and-Bricks business (Soopramanien, 2011). Meanwhile, although the number of Internet users is growing significantly, the number of online shoppers remains low. To boost conversion of website visitors to customers, it is crucial for vendors to reduce these risks. The success of online vendors depends more on customers continuing to use their services to purchase products than on their initial adoption. For instance, an online business starts making profits from the average consumer after the fourth order (Chiu et al., 2009), as long as it is more expensive to win a new customer than to maintain an existing one. Consequently, it is essential for online retailers not only to attract new customers, but also to maintain socially sustainable relationships with the previous ones. Then, online businesses need to redefine their strategies to meet customer expectations and win their trust. As in which is deemed to be one of the most non-trivial variables to consider in Online buying behavior research (Liao et al., 2017; Harris & Goode, 2004).

Marketers and online retailers need to focus on the attitudes and e-behaviors of Internet users to win new customers and retain existing ones. Online businesses' understanding of customers' repurchasing behavior enables them to achieve their targeted results and benefits.

Our research provides guidance for online businesses to identify the antecedents of online purchase and repurchase intention and, therefore, to

study the factors influencing Online customers' intention, so that e-commerce companies can implement appropriate business strategies involving technology, web design and marketing plans. Although research on online repurchase intention is widespread in the literature, research explaining the relationship between social/psychological factors (trust and perceived risk), utilitarian factors (perceived usefulness, ease of use), website reputation and online repurchase intention is scarce, and the results of some studies are contradictory. Thus, the main objective of this study is to develop an explanatory model of online repurchase intention, integrating antecedents cited in the following three fields: information systems, marketing and social psychology, and to test empirically this model to validate the causal relationships. This research will extend existing knowledge and provides contributions to the literature of the online consumer behavior.

In the first section, we begin by reviewing factors that are deemed antecedents of online repurchase intention, such as e-trust, perceived risk, perceived utility, perceived ease of use, and website reputation. We highlight the dependency of the online repurchase behavior on few factors. Then, we discuss how these factors, as an attempt at fit, are expected to affect online repurchase intention. In the second and third section, we describe the research method and results. In the final section, we discuss the theoretical and managerial implications of the findings and conclude with limitations and avenues for future research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Research on repurchase intention has a rich history spanning for more than five decades. However, research on online repurchase intention is still recent and truncated toward factors and antecedents. In this field, research include utilitarian factors (perceived ease of use and usefulness), social/psychological factors (perceived risk and e-trust) and a factor linked to the website's reputation.

Meanwhile, the theories that are incremented in the present research are mainly Expectation-Confirmation Model (Bhattacharjee, 2001), the theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003) and the theory of Trust-Commitment (Morgan & Hunt, 1994).

2.1. Online Repurchase Intention

This study examines Online Repurchase Intention as the dependent variable, based on the theory of reasoned action proposed by Ajzen and Fishbein (1980). Intention is found to be one of the most relevant factors to explain the relationship between attitude and behavior and is the most convenient for adequate construct to examine consumers' behavior (Ajzen, 2008).

Online customer behavior is an ongoing issue in Marketing areas. Researchers have studied online customer retention in different contexts, such as "Online Repurchase Intention" (Khalifa & Liu, 2007). Therefore, research attempted to demonstrate that offline repurchase intention is influenced by the initial use and purchase experience. In an online shopping context, the Online Repurchase Intention is widely different from offline repurchase intention. For instance, factors affecting Online Repurchase Intention is intended to be different from the ones affecting the repurchase intention in physical stores (Guan & Cheng, 2009; Hellier et al., 2003; Rezaei & Amin, 2013).

Thus, the goal of this study is to highlight the importance utilitarian factors in affecting customers' Online Repurchase Intention.

2.2. E-trust and Online Repurchase Intention

Trust alludes to accomplish building sustainable and profitable economic relationships between vendors and customers, especially in an online environment. The separation between customers and vendors in online purchasing creates a specific environment, in which trust is of vital importance. Trust in an online retailer is seen as "one party's subjective assessment that another party will perform a particular transaction according to his or her confident expectations, in an environment characterized by uncertainty" (Pavlou & Ba, 2002). If there were trust, customers would believe that the seller could deliver the goods and services in an appropriate manner. Trust is customers' belief in the benevolence, competence and integrity of salespeople. Benevolence is the customer's belief that salespeople do not behave opportunistically against them. Competence represents a salesperson's ability to fulfill his or her obligations in line with customer expectations. As for integrity, it focuses on a customer's beliefs about salespeople's willingness to honor their responsibility (Chou & Hsu, 2016; Bulut, 2015). Most of studies consider trust in online shopping as a key predictor of a first purchase and have neglected its impact on continued website use and repeat purchases. The objective of this research is to study Online Repurchase Intention, in which we

are primarily interested in trust at the post-purchase stage. It is largely distinct from pre-purchase trust because customers already have an experience with the online business and based on this experience, they tend to re-evaluate their perceptions of trust and modify their repurchase decisions (Yulia & Dan, 2018). Therefore, the violation of trust in online commerce generates negative repurchase intention (Goles et al., 2009). For Mayer et al. (1995) risky behavior, such as the repurchase decision, is a function of trust and the perceived risk of the behavior. If the level of trust exceeds the perceived risk cut offs, customers are ready to adopt repurchase behavior (Zhang & Nuangjamnong, 2023; Fang et al., 2014). Thus, customers' trust on the website not only reduces their perception uncertainty but also acts as an impediment in their intention to move to another website.

The success of online sales essentially depends on customers' trust in vendors and products (Shin et al., 2013). The degree of trust depends on the online seller's ability to satisfy customers (Liao et al., 2017) (Zhang et al., 2011). Thus, trust establishes the vendor's credibility and enables the customer to successfully complete transactions on the website, and get what was promised, in a way that motivates them to make future online transactions (Fang et al., 2014). Customers express a strong intention to repurchase online when they trust the website. This shows that trust is a determining factor in long-term relationships between customers and online vendors (Jayathilaka, 2020; Fang et al., 2014). In this sense, E-trust gives rise for disposition to Online Repurchase Intention, and leads to the following hypothesis:

H1: E-trust affects positively Online Repurchase Intention.

2.3. Perceived risk and Online Repurchase Intention

Perceived risk is "the customer's perception of the uncertainty and potential adverse consequences of purchasing a product or service" (Al-Smadi, 2012). Marketing Research have shown that Perceived risk has a considerable impact on consumer behavior (Cunningham et al., 2005), so risk and its tolerance affect the customer's evaluation, choice and decision to purchase a product or service. In the context of e-commerce, risk is the customer's perception that the online purchase may have negative consequences or undesirable outcomes (Glover & Benbasat, 2010). The absence of physical interaction between customers and vendors in e-commerce and the unpredictable nature of Internet technology create uncertainty for transactions' output (Pavlou, 2003).

Furthermore, Perceived risk can arise from download delays and weak security (Chang & Chen, 2008), and can arise from payment transactions, as well as from the product itself. Customers fear the opportunistic behavior of the online salespersons; for instance breach of delivery commitments, unjustifiable delay in product delivery, and receipt of payment without delivering a product, etc.). Therefore, customers' orders do not meet their expectations; as long as, they worry about privacy and their personal data (Gašper et al., 2018; Glover & Benbasat, 2010). Thus, online retailers abuse customer's trust (Lee et al., 2011).

Previous research suggest that Perceived risk affects negatively online shopping. Researchers have found that the uncertainty of the online environment is one of the main factors discouraging customers from placing orders, and that only one-third of attempts to complete online transactions led to purchases (Dinev & Hart, 2006).

We recognize that buyers fear toward online salespersons' opportunism, confidentiality and information security issues affects positively Perceived risk and consequently it affects negatively their purchase intention. Perceived risk is also a determinant of repurchase intention, which only occurs when online buyers have already carried out an initial transaction with the website (Hellier et al., 2003). This means that buyers already have experience with the seller and becomes predisposed to make new purchase decisions (Fang et al., 2014). Repurchase intention can be seen as "the customer's subjective of revisiting an online store, taking into account their current situation or likely circumstances" (Yulia et al., 2018). Mwencha et al. (2014) show that Perceived risk is an antecedent of continued use of online sales services, although its negative affect.

When the online salesperson respects transactional duties, the perception of risk and uncertainty will be lower, and customers are willing to repurchase from the same website (Pavlou et al., 2007). On the other hand, customers tend to avoid future exchange relationships if they see that the salesperson has not kept his promises (Chiu et al., 2012). Thus, we assume that the greater the Perceived risk is the less likely the online repurchase occurs. We postulate the following hypothesis:

H2: Perceived risk affects negatively Online Repurchase Intention.

2.4. Perceived usefulness and Online Repurchase Intention

Davis et al. (1989) proposed the technology

acceptance model, whose main objective is to study the determinants of computer application adoption (Al Shibly, 2011; Davis, 1989). According to this model, users' intention to adopt computer applications depends on its Perceived usefulness, which is, by definition "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would improve his or her performance at work". Although, initially the technology acceptance model focused on the use of systems in workplace, recently it has been applied in the area of online shopping.

The usefulness of a website depends on the advantages offered to customers. These benefits stem from both technological efficiency through obtaining ordered products or services. According to the technology acceptance model, the Perceived usefulness of a website is deemed a key determinant of purchase intention and is among the strongest predictors of the customer's intention to continue buying, as it improves both the perception of the website and the buying experience.

Empirical studies have shown that the Perceived usefulness of a website is a determinant of repurchase intention (Hung et al., 2013; Kim & Malhotra, 2005). Similarly, Bhattacharjee's (2001) proved that Perceived usefulness is a key factor in customer repurchase intention. Customers intend to repurchase products from a website that provides quick access and a convenient purchasing process (Mei-Hui et al., 2018; Liao et al., 2017). However, Shang et al. (2005) were unable to highlight a link between Perceived usefulness and Online Repurchase Intention. Consequently, the above analysis leads to the following hypothesis:

H3: Perceived usefulness of website affects positively Online Repurchase Intention.

2.5. Perceived ease of use and Online Repurchase Intention

Davis (1989) proposed the technology acceptance. The decision to use a new technology depends on both its Perceived usefulness and its Perceived ease of use. These two variables also underlie the intention to buy online. Perceived ease of use is found to be a nontrivial factor in determining online repurchasing behavior. This concept is defined as "the degree to which a consumer perceives the ease of connecting with a web-based company and can obtain the product they are looking for" (Wen et al., 2011). When customers overcome difficulties to interact with e-commerce websites, to search for product information, and get the relevant products and proceed for the online payment, they are highly motivated to make new purchases (Wen et al., 2011).

Rezaei and Amin (2013) and Tehreem (2016) demonstrated a significant relationship between Perceived ease of use and Online Purchase Intention. The authors came out with the impact of Perceived ease of use of online shopping on repeated purchases. Ease of navigation improves the consumer's online shopping experience and can lead to greater satisfaction and purchase pleasure (Liao et al., 2017).

According to the previous analysis, we propose the following hypothesis:

H4: Perceived ease of use affects positively Online Repurchase Intention.

2.6. Website reputation and online Repurchase Intention

Perceived reputation is the result of a company's interactions with its environment. These interactions shape information that help customers to appreciate thoroughly the quality of the offer (Yoon et al., 1993). From a global perspective, reputation can be associated with a company's credibility and is the consequence of comparing what the company has promised to what has been delivered (Casalo et al., 2008). Thus, reputation is viewed as a signal of a company's honesty (Doney & Cannon, 1997). However, in the online environment, reputation is a nontrivial variable than just a peripheral signal; it involves the collective social knowledge of a website's trustworthiness (Bansal et al., 2008). For Chiles and McMackin (1996), reputation leads customers to believe that the seller will act in their best interests. It involves customers' perception of the website's public image, its innovative character, the quality of its products and services, and its commitment to customer's satisfaction (Zhang et al., 2011). Thus, a website's reputation is, the overall assessment of a website's product and service

expertise, consumer experience and effective communications about the company's credibility in serving customers (Li, 2014). The website interaction leads customers to appreciate the seller's offerings and values (Casalo et al., 2008). As a result, customers determine the reputation of the website based on their assessment of the previous behaviors and performance of online vendors.

The established reputation and image of the website enable customers to evaluate new products offered on the site and stimulates them to repurchase (Delgado et al., 2008). Some researchers show that a positive reputation can lead to a new purchase and helps develop sales and market share (Shapiro, 1982) and increase customer loyalty (Andreassen & Lindestad, 1998; Robertson, 1993; Mei-Hui et al., 2018). Thus, Kotha et al. (2001) suggest that reputation-building activities can be a key determinant of success for online businesses. Resnick and Zeckhauser (2002) cite eBay and Google as examples of the best-known service companies that, thanks to their good reputation, currently achieve high profitability and a loyal customer portfolio.

Thus, the above analysis leads to the following hypothesis:

H5: Website reputation affects positively Online Repurchase Intention.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The literature review and hypotheses generation provide guidance for developing a conceptual model, to identify the determinants of Online Repurchase Intention, which describe the relationships between the variables. As a result, we propose the conceptual framework that highlights the relationships between the factors and the Online Repurchase Intention with their signs:

Figure1: Conceptual Framework.

3.1. METHODOLOGY

3.1.1. Sampling

This study is intended to Tunisian e-commerce sites. Data were collected using a survey, which implemented face-to-face Internet from a convenience sample (See Appendix), who had already made online purchases. Consistent with prior studies on online repurchase behavior, participants were asked to recall their last online purchase and name the purchase website, then asked to complete the questionnaire based on their selection. We collected 220 questionnaires, among which 60.9% (134 participants) were women; 59.5% (132 respondents) have graduate degrees and 25% (55 respondents) have bachelor's degrees. The

majority of respondents are between the ages of 20 and 50 (See Appendix).

3.1.2. Measures

A structured survey instrument was developed. We first defined each construct's domain and then drafted items to reflect the conceptual domain of a particular construct, based on a review of the literature and field interviews. We relied on reflective scales developed and implemented in previous research, using a five-point Likert scale, for each item. Through an iterative process with evaluation and feedback from consumer behavior academics and people who are involved in online purchasing, we developed the final questionnaire.

Table 1: Measurement Items.

Variables	Scales	Sources
E-trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "The website correctly delivers me a product that matches the description displayed". - "There is no discrepancy between the delivery conditions published on the website before and the services after purchase (e.g. quality, tracking, S/A, etc.)". - "I think the buying website is honest". - "Overall, I trust the buying website". 	Pavlou and Ba (2002)
Perceived risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "The overall purchasing process on the website carries a high degree of risk or uncertainty". - "There was a high degree of risk or uncertainty when purchasing the product on the website". 	Pavlou et al. (2007)
Perceived usefulness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "The website improved my shopping performance (for example, the transaction was processed" quickly). 	

	- "The transaction process on the website has improved my efficiency in the purchase of products". - "I think the purchase website has been very useful in the purchase of the products".	Davis (1989)
Perceived ease of use	- "The online shopping site is easy to use". - "The purchasing website is flexible to interact with". - "It is easier to use the internet to find the products I want to buy".	Davis (1989) Gefen et al. (2003)
Website reputation	- "The shopping website has a good reputation with its customers". - "The shopping website is well known by people". - "The purchase website has a favorable rating".	Jarvenpaa et al. (1999)
Online Repurchase Intention	- "If I had to buy the product again, I would probably buy it on the same website". - "If I could, I would like to reuse the website for my next purchase". - "I intend to review the website in the future". - "I would like to revisit the website to buy products in the near future".	Gefen (2000) Jarvenpaa et al. (2000)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We assess the validity and the reliability of the constructs first by using SPSS (version 23 for Windows) to conduct an exploratory factor analysis of all the items used to measure the six first-order reflective latent constructs in the model.

Finally, we tested the relationships between the dependent variable (Online Repurchase Intention) and the independent variables (E-trust, Perceived

risk, Perceived usefulness, Perceived ease of use, Website reputation) using the single and multiple linear regression method.

4.1. Exploratory Analysis

Table 2 shows the reliability of the measurement scales, deduce the factors of each concept and study the unidimensionality of the measurement scales.

Table 2: Exploratory Factor Analysis.

Scales Reliability		Factor Analysis				
Cronbach'α		KMO	Bartlett Test	Significance	Explained Variance	Number of Factors
E-trust	0,933	0,666	872,508	0,000	84,157	1
Perceived risk	0,925	0,5	293,149	0,000	93,017	1
Perceived usefulness	0,941	0,761	597,339	0,000	89,472	1
Perceived ease of use	0,923	0,745	511,961	0,000	86,844	1
Web site reputation	0,942	0,737	627,178	0,000	89,633	1
Online Repurchase Intention	0,960	0,763	1111,488	0,000	89,556	1

The reliability of the measurement scales was tested using the correlation coefficient "Cronbach Alpha". The results of the test show that all the values found in the Cronbach's alpha statistic exceed 0.7 (Peterson, 1995), which emphasizes good internal consistency of the measurement scales. With regard to the factor analysis, the results found make it possible to make the following findings:

- The scales studied are one-dimensional,
- Most KMO values are satisfactory and exceed 0.5, which means that data are ready to split to factors (Akrou, 2000). The Bartlett test of

sphericity is significant. These results prove the internal consistency of the constructs.

The analysis of the variance shows that for each scale the percentage of the variance restored by the extracted factor is greater than the recommended of 50%.

4.2. Regression Analysis

Regression results show that the model is globally significant with a significant Fisher coefficient ($F = 192.603$, $p < 0.001$). They also show that the R^2 value is 0.818, leading to a good quality of linear

adjustment. The correlation coefficient (R^2) shows that the model returns 81.8% of the variability of the Online Repurchase Intention. Therefore, it is possible to proceed to the analysis of individual significance of the variables.

- The effect of E-trust on Online Repurchase Intention

Table 3 shows that E-trust has a positive and significant impact on the Online Repurchase Intention, which allows us to confirm the H1 hypothesis. This result is congruent with the one of Yulia and Dan (2018).

Table 3: E-trust affects Online Repurchase Intention.

Online Repurchase Intention and E-trust				
	Standardized Bêta	t-Student	Sig	R ²
E-trust	0,62	11,956	0,000	0,384

- The effect of Perceived risk on Online Repurchase Intention

Table 4 shows that the Perceived Risk has a significant negative effect on online repurchase intention. This result leads to confirm H2 hypothesis. This result is congruent with those of Mwencha et al. (2014) and means that customers tend to avoid future trading relationships if they deem the level of risks dealing with the seller is high.

Table 4: Perceived risk affects Online Repurchase Intention.

Online Repurchase Intention and Perceived Risk				
	Standardized Bêta	t-Student	Sig	R ²
Perceived risk	-0,423	-6,889	0,000	0,179

- The effect of Perceived usefulness on Online Repurchase Intention

The approved relationship between the Perceived usefulness and the Online Repurchase Intention confirms H3 hypothesis (see Table 5). The Perceived usefulness of online shopping can lead to repetitive purchases. This result is congruent with the ones of Liao et al. (2017) and Hung et al (2013).

Table 5: Perceived usefulness affects Online Repurchase Intention.

Online Repurchase Intention and Perceived usefulness				
	Standardized Bêta	t-Student	Sig	R ²
Perceived usefulness	0,722	15,401	0,000	0,521

- Perceived ease of use affects the Online Repurchase Intention

Table 6 shows that Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on the Online Repurchase Intention. This result is aligned with the

studies of Zhang and Nuangjamnong (2023) and Tehreem (2016). This result confirms the H4 hypothesis and shows that when customers do not find it difficult to interact with websites, to search for product information, to have the products as well as to pay online, they are very motivated to make new purchases.

Table 6: Perceived ease of use affects the Online Repurchase Intention.

Online Repurchase Intention and Perceived ease of use				
	Standardized Bêta	t-Student	Sig	R ²
Perceived ease of use	0,62	11,659	0,000	0,384

- Website reputation affects Online Repurchase Intention

The relationship between the Website reputation and the Online Repurchase Intention (Table 7) is proved to be positive and significant. As a result, hypothesis H5 is approved. These findings are consistent with previous research that has verified a positive effect of the Website reputation on Online Repurchase Intention (Mei-hui et al., 2018; Casalo et al., 2008). Meanwhile, results show that customer's perception of website image, innovativeness, products and services quality and its commitment to consumer satisfaction have a positive effect on Online Repurchase Intention.

Table 7: Website reputation affects Online Repurchase Intention.

Online Repurchase Intention and website reputation				
	Standardized Bêta	t-Student	Sig	R ²
Website reputation	0,846	23,442	0,000	0,716

4.3. Discussion

According to the regression results, we assume that factors mentioned above affect positively customers online repurchase intention. When customers trust the website, feel safe (low risk), see value and ease in using it, and view it as reputable, they are significantly more likely to repurchase. These factors work synergistically to reduce friction, enhance satisfaction, and build loyalty.

All five factors build customer satisfaction and confidence, which are key predictors of Online Repurchase Intention. They reduce barriers, enhance the experience, and foster a positive perception that makes customers return.

5. CONCLUSION

5.1. Theoretical Implications

This study fosters two specific theoretical

contributions to consumer behavior literature. The first theoretical contribution is the understanding of Online Repurchase Intention. We suggest that some of the conflicting results in the literature is explained by the conflation of hedonic versus utilitarian factors. Although early researchers conceptually recognized the influence of hedonic motivations on online purchase intention, through perception of online prices (Santo & Marques, 2022), utilitarian factors seem to be more affecting Online Repurchase Intention.

The primary objective of this study is to highlight antecedents of the Online Repurchase Intention, focusing on utilitarian factors. Empirical results indicate that the five hypotheses of the conceptual model are validated. They show that Perceived usefulness, Perceived ease of use, E-trust, Website reputation and Perceived risk are important factors, and that the first four factors are positively linked to repurchase intention, while Perceived risk negatively affects Online Repurchase Intention. This means that a useful shopping website can encourage customers to repeat the buying decision, likewise, if the website is easy to navigate (provides quick search, convenient shopping process, quick access), it will also increase repurchase decision. The results showed that customers are concerned about risks, payment security and the confidentiality of their information. The study also indicates that customers with high levels of trust express a strong repurchase intention.

5.2. Managerial Implications

On one hand, online shopping managers are supposed to take into consideration the utilitarian factors to improve the attributes and characteristics of services and simplify online transaction processes, in order to make the website more useful, user-friendly, compatible with customer requirements and easy to use regardless of the level of IT skills of the user.

On the other hand, online shopping managers should emphasize the reliability of their online shopping information system. E-retailers must, therefore, ensure the confidentiality of content and transactions and protect customers' personal and financial information against intruder attacks. Tremendous concern with confidentiality is required when designing the website e-commerce to secure payments and preserve privacy, which constitutes a positive lead to trust reinforcement and relationship commitment.

Strengthening the confidence of their users in

Appendix:

online shopping. Online shop managers can use several methods to strengthen the confidence of their online customers. One is to show customers that they are not behaving opportunistically against them, that they are fulfilling their duties and responsibilities. Online shop managers have an interest in responding quickly to customer messages and complaints. They are also encouraged to provide more secure payment systems, data security and privacy policies.

Finally, building favorable reputation, as the reputation and image of the website allows regular customers to evaluate new products offered on the site and stimulates them to repurchase. Good reputation is a key determinant of success for online businesses.

5.3. Limitations and Future Research

Several limitations have been identified. First, when conducting the survey, respondents answered questions based on various e-commerce websites, rather than responding to questions about a specific business type of the website (B2B or B2C). Indeed, it is likely to have effect on customers' experience and perceptions of online shopping, and consequently their online repurchase behavior. The focus on business customers's Online Repurchase Intention may lead to relevant findings on perceived switching costs (procedural, financial and relational) once a decision should be made to search for another web site and/or e-commerce channels. Further research could implement a Multi-Group Analysis to demonstrate the obvious differences in the effects of various types of websites on Online Repurchase Intention. Second, the online shopping customers may be attracted to some websites rather than others according to their cultural backgrounds and different shopping intention. Future research are invited to investigate the website congruence with cultural preferences, as a factor affecting Online Repurchase Intention.

The third limitation concerns the scope of sampling. Indeed, examining the Online Repurchase Intention and/or decision making in other cultures could emphasize the diverse levels of customers' trust and commitment and the contextual/situational factors.

Moreover, studies on online customers' emphasizing of their perceptions and expectations could enrich the present research findings. Scrutinizing the perceived performance of the customers' online repurchase decision could come up with relevant recommendations on the brand's website architecture and the e-commerce structure.

Sample Characteristics.

Variables		Size	Pourcentage
Gender	Men	86	39,1
	Women	134	60,9
Age	Under 20 years	14	6,4
	[20,30[78	35,5
	[30, 50[104	47,3
	Above 50 years	24	10,9
Educational Level	College	34	15,45
	Certificate of Secondary Studies	55	25
	Bachelor Degree	131	59,54

REFERENCES

- Adnan, H. (2014). An analysis of the factors affecting online purchasing behavior of Pakistani customers. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 6(5), 133-148.
- Ajzen, I. (2008). Consumer attitudes and behavior. In C. P. Haugtvedt, P. M. Herr, & F. R. Kardes (Eds.), *Handbook of consumer psychology* (pp. 525-548). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. Prentice Hall.
- Akrout, F. (2000, February 2). Méthodes d'analyse des données de deuxième génération et applications en marketing. *Séminaire de méthodologie de recherche en gestion, LIGUE, Tunis*.
- Al Shibly, H. (2011). Human resources information systems success assessment: An integrative model. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 5(5), 157-169.
- Al-Smadi, M. O. (2012). Factors affecting adoption of electronic banking: An analysis of the perspectives of banks' customers. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(17), 294-309.
- Andreassen, T. W., & Lindestad, B. (1998). The effect of corporate image in the formation of customer loyalty. *Journal of Service Research*, 1(1), 82-92.
- Bansal, G., Zahedi, F. M., & Gefen, D. (2008). The moderating influence of privacy concern on the efficacy of privacy assurance mechanisms for building trust: A multiple context investigation. In *Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Information Systems*. Paris, France.
- Bhattacharjee, A. (2001). An empirical analysis of the antecedents of electronic commerce service continuance. *Decision Support Systems*, 32(2), 201-214.
- Bulut, Z. A. (2015). Determinants of repurchase intention in online shopping: A Turkish consumer's perspective. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(10), 55-63.
- Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C., & Guinalíu, M. (2008). The role of perceived usability, reputation, satisfaction and consumer familiarity on the website loyalty formation process. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24(2), 325-345.
- Chang, H. H., & Chen, S. W. (2008). The impact of online store environment cues on purchase intention: Trust and perceived risk as mediators. *Online Information Review*, 32(6), 818-841.
- Chiles, T. H., & McMackin, J. F. (1996). Integrating variable risk preferences, trust, and transaction cost economics. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(1), 73-99.
- Chiu, C. M., Chang, C. C., Cheng, H. L., & Fang, Y. H. (2009). Determinants of customer repurchase intention in online shopping. *Online Information Review*, 33(4), 761-784.
- Chiu, C. M., Hsu, M. H., Lai, H., & Chang, C. M. (2012). Re-examining the influence of trust on online repeat purchase intention: The moderating role of habit and its antecedents. *Decision Support Systems*, 53, 835-845.
- Chou, S. W., & Hsu, C. S. (2016). Understanding online repurchase intention: Social exchange theory and shopping habit. *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, 14, 19-45.
- Cunningham, L. F., Gerlach, J., & Harper, M. D. (2005). Perceived risk and e-banking services: An analysis from the perspective of the consumer. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 10(1), 65-78.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340.
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical models. *Management Science*, 35(8), 982-1003.
- Delgado-Ballester, E., & Hernández-Espallardo, M. (2008). Effect of brand associations on consumer reactions to unknown online brands. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 12(3), 81-113.
- Dinev, T., & Hart, P. (2006). An extended privacy calculus model for e-commerce transactions. *Information*

- Systems Research, 17(1), 61–80.
- Doney, P. M., & Cannon, J. P. (1997). An examination of the nature of trust in the buyer–seller relationship. *Journal of Marketing*, 61(2), 35–51.
- Fang, Y., Qureshi, I., Sun, H., McCole, P., Ramsey, E., & Lim, K. H. (2014). Trust, satisfaction, and online repurchase intention: The moderating role of perceived effectiveness of e-commerce institutional mechanisms. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(2), 407–427.
- Gasper, J., Robert, L., & Miha, M. (2018). Impact of fear of identity theft and perceived risk on online purchase intention. *Organizacija*, 51(2), 145–155.
- Gefen, D. (2000). E-commerce: The role of familiarity and trust. *Omega: The International Journal of Management Science*, 28(6), 725–737.
- Gefen, D., Karahanna, E., & Straub, D. W. (2003). Trust and TAM in online shopping: An integrated model. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(4), 533–556.
- Glover, S., & Benbasat, I. (2010). A comprehensive model of perceived risk of e-commerce transactions. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 15(2), 47–78.
- Goles, T., Rao, S. V., Lee, S., & Warren, J. (2009). Trust violation in electronic commerce: Customer concerns and reactions. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 49(4), 1–9.
- Guan, H. L., & Cheng, B. D. (2009). Analysis on the consumer's online information search behavior. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on E-Business and Information System Security* (pp. 1–4).
- Harris, L. C., & Goode, M. M. H. (2004). The four levels of loyalty and the pivotal role of trust: A study of online service dynamics. *Journal of Retailing*, 80(2), 139–158.
- Hellier, P. K., Geursen, G. M., Carr, R. A., & Rickard, J. A. (2003). Customer repurchase intention: A general structural equation model. *European Journal of Marketing*, 37(11/12), 1762–1800.
- Hung, S. Y., Chang, C. M., & Kuo, S. R. (2013). User acceptance of mobile e-government services: An empirical study. *Government Information Quarterly*, 30(1), 33–44.
- Jarvenpaa, S. L., Tractinsky, N., & Vitale, M. (1999). Consumer trust in an Internet store: A cross-cultural validation. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 5(2), 1–35.
- Jarvenpaa, S. L., Tractinsky, N., & Vitale, M. (2000). Consumer trust in an Internet store. *Information Technology and Management*, 1(1–2), 45–71.
- Jayathilaka, K. K. R. A. (2020). Relationship between online repurchase intention and e-satisfaction: Quantitative research study based on young people in Western Province in Sri Lanka. *Open Access Library Journal*, 7(12), 1–10.
- Khalifa, M., & Liu, V. (2007). Online consumer retention: Contingent effects of online shopping habit and online shopping experience. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 16, 780–792.
- Kim, S. S., & Malhotra, N. K. (2005). A longitudinal model of continued IS use: An integrative view of four mechanisms underlying post-adoption phenomena. *Management Science*, 51(5), 741–755.
- Kotha, S., Rajgopal, S., & Rindova, V. (2001). Reputation building and performance: An empirical analysis of the top-50 pure Internet firms. *European Management Journal*, 19(6), 571–586.
- Lee, C. H., Eze, U. C., & Ndubisi, N. (2011). Analyzing key determinants of online repurchase intentions. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 23(2), 200–221.
- Li, Y. (2014). The impact of disposition to privacy: Website reputation and website familiarity on information privacy concerns. *Decision Support Systems*, 57, 343–354.
- Liao, C., Lin, H. N., Luo, M. M., & Chea, S. (2017). Factors influencing online shoppers' repurchase intentions: The roles of satisfaction and regret. *Information & Management*, 54(5), 651–668.
- Mayer, R. C., Davis, J. H., & Schoorman, F. D. (1995). An integrative model of organizational trust. *Academy of Management Review*, 20, 709–734.
- Mei-Hui, P., Bireswar, D., & Shu-Lung, S. (2018). Evaluating the role of trust and satisfaction on consumer repurchase intention: A study in Taiwan context. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, 16(8), 58–73.
- Morgan, R. M., & Hunt, S. D. (1994). The commitment-trust theory of relationship marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 58, 20–38.
- Mwencha, M. P., Muathe, M. S., & Kuria, T. J. (2014). Effects of perceived attributes, perceived risk and perceived value on usage of online retailing services. *Journal of Management Research*, 6(2), 140–161.
- Pavlou, P. A. (2003). Consumer acceptance of electronic commerce: Integrating trust and risk with the technology acceptance model. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 7(3), 69–103.

- Pavlou, P. A., & Ba, S. (2002). Evidence of the effect of trust building technology in electronic markets: Price premium and buyer behavior. *MIS Quarterly*, 26(3), 243–268.
- Pavlou, P. A., Huigang, L., & Yajiong, X. (2007). Understanding and mitigating uncertainty in online exchange relationships: A principal-agent perspective. *MIS Quarterly*, 31(1), 105–136.
- Peterson, R. A. (1995). Une méta-analyse du coefficient alpha de Cronbach. *Recherche et Applications en Marketing*, 10(2), 75–88.
- Pobee, F. (2021). Assessing online repurchase intention in a developing country: The role of perceived value. *International Journal of Strategic Decision Sciences*, 12(1), 61–76.
- Resnick, P., & Zeckhauser, R. (2002). Trust among strangers in Internet transactions: Empirical analysis of eBay's reputation system. *Advances in Applied Microeconomics*, 11, 127–157.
- Rezaei, S., & Amin, M. (2013). Exploring online repurchase behavioural intention of university students in Malaysia. *Journal of Global Business Advancement*, 6(2), 92–119.
- Robertson, T. S. (1993). How to reduce market penetration cycle times. *Sloan Management Review*, 35(1), 87–96.
- Santo, P. E., & Marques, A. M. A. (2022). Determinants of the online purchase intention: Hedonic motivations, prices, information and trust. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 17(1), 56–71.
- Shang, A. R., Chen, Y. C., & Shen, L. (2005). Extrinsic versus intrinsic motivations for customers to shop online. *Information & Management*, 42(3), 401–413.
- Shapiro, C. (1982). Consumer information, product quality, and seller reputation. *The Bell Journal of Economics*, 13, 20–35.
- Shin, J. I., Chung, K. H., Oh, J. S., & Lee, C. W. (2013). The effect of site quality on repurchase intention in Internet shopping through mediating variables: The case of university students in South Korea. *International Journal of Information Management*, 33(3), 453–463.
- Soopramanien, D. (2011). Conflicting attitudes and skepticism towards online shopping: The role of experience. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 35(3), 338–347.
- Tehreem, A. (2016). Factors deriving customers' repurchase intention in online shopping: A Pakistani consumer's perspective. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 5(12), 291–270.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., & Davis, G. B. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425–478.
- Wen, C., Prybutok, V. R., & Xu, C. (2011). An integrated model for customer online repurchase intention. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 52(1), 14–23.
- Yoon, E., Guffey, H. G., & Kijewski, V. (1993). The effects of information and company reputation on intentions to buy a business service. *Journal of Business Research*, 27, 215–228.
- Yulia, W. S., & Dan, J. K. (2018). Assessing the effects of customers' product evaluations and trust on repurchase intention in e-commerce environments. *International Journal of Information Management*, 39, 199–219.
- Zhang, Y., Fang, Y., Wei, K. K., Ramsey, E., McCole, P., & Chen, H. (2011). Repurchase intention in B2C e-commerce: A relationship quality perspective. *Information & Management*, 48(6), 192–200.
- Zhang, Z., & Nuangjamnong, C. (2023). The impact factors toward online repurchase intention: A case study of Taobao e-commerce platform in China. *International Research E-Journal on Business and Economics*, 7(2), 35–56.